

ISic1324

I.Sicily inscription 1324

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140818

1. Κούλντος Σόσσις
2. καὶ Πετρονία
3. Σοσσία Χεία
4. τῆ θυγατρὶ, ζησάση
5. ἔτη □ ἰ □ ἡμέρα (ς) □ κ□β'.
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492930

EDCS 39101695

PHI 140818

Bibliography

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Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0503 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5728

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